

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Learning action cell sessions on shared pedagogical practices of seasoned and Millennial teachers: Strengthening 21st century learning

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Abstract

The study determined the improvement of the seasoned and millennial teachers to strengthen 21st century learning using LAC sessions on shared pedagogical practices at Malinao Elementary School and Pulong Duhat Primary School in San Miguel, Bulacan during the School Year 2019-2020. COT-RPMS tools were used to describe the pedagogical practices of both seasoned and millennial teachers and it is also used to determine their pedagogical needs to be developed. LAC sessions on shared pedagogical practices were implemented to improve their practices. The self- Reflection method was used on every LAC session to know their learnings. Interview guide questions were also used to determine the teachers' experiences on LAC sessions on shared pedagogical practices. Using the qualitative method of research with 9 teacher-participants as subjects of the study, findings showed that teachers obtained low ratings on the third quarter classroom observations and obtained high ratings on the fourth quarter classroom observations. High ratings were found between the third and fourth observations on the teachers' pedagogical practices. Moreover, these teachers agreed that they had positive feedback on LAC sessions on shared pedagogical practices. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the use of LAC sessions on shared pedagogical practices of seasoned and millennial teachers could really strengthen 21st century learning.

Keywords: Seasoned Teachers; Millennial Teachers; Learning Action Cell Sessions; Pedagogical Practices; 21st Century Learning; Generation Z.

1. Introduction

The necessity to prepare a new world for tomorrow's youth needs to be adapted to change. The 21st century educators must create a curriculum that will help students to connect with the world and understand the issues that the world faces. For better understanding of today's learners, the cultural differences of different generations involved in the educational system must be given emphasis.

The generations that are currently in the educational system are: Gen X, Y and Z. The Generation Z which consists of the 21st century learners and refers to babies born from the mid-2000s through today, although the term isn't widely used yet. This may signal the end of 'alphabet soup' (it does coincide with the literal end of the alphabet, after all). A flurry of potential labels has appeared, including Gen Tech, post-Millennials, iGeneration, and Gen Y-Fi (Kasasa, 2019).

The characteristics of 21st century learners are discussed in three categories: The technological learner; The all-knowing learner; and the literate learner (Nudalo, 2018). The technological learners, the 21st century learners are referred to as the "screen generation" because they are so much more visually oriented than any generation before them. The all-knowing learner, the 21st century learner knows "everything". The literate learner, 21st century learner

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possesses good communication skills; are adaptable and innovative; and can easily solve complex problems. They are comfortable working with technology in order to broaden their knowledge.

On the other hand, the 21st century teachers need to understand the meaning of innovative pedagogical practices when recognizing the concept; it concerns with attempts to initiate reform within the classroom along with incorporation of technological resources that have stimulated the birth of the information society. Keeping pace with the developments of the age, audio-visual equipment, computers, and other tools of communication have steadily found their place within the walls of educational institutions and the process of reforming pedagogical practice.

Furthermore, learners of the 21st century are educated with the intention of them becoming productive citizens in a democratic society in terms of what is required in the 21st century workplace. As a result, these learners possess certain characteristics that are part of the new millennium. These come with new challenges for the 21st century teacher.

Conversely, the teachers currently in the workplace are the Gen X and Gen Y. They should be given emphasis because the success of education lies on their hands. Without their effectiveness, DepEd vision and mission will be nonsense. Understanding and appreciating different generation is critical for effective and productive teams, department and organization.

Generation X or also known as Gen X consists of the people who were born between 1965 - 1979 and are currently between 40-54 years old. It is also called the “middle child” of generation; they are independent, resourceful, and self-sufficient. They value freedom and responsibility in the workplace. Many in this generation display a casual disdain for authority and structured work hours. The seasoned teachers fall in this generation (Kasasa, 2019).

The Seasoned Teacher can also be characterized based on their teaching expertise since, the best criterion for seasoned teacher lies in their expertise (Yazdanmehr et al., 2016) and length of service. They possess expertise in the content area, and familiarity with the school and their students and have good communication to parents and co-workers. The length of teaching service of a seasoned teacher can be measured from 5 years and above. Moreover, teachers with more than 20 years of experience in teaching are more effective than teachers with no experience but are not much more effective than those with 5 years of experience (Kini, and Podolsky, 2016).

Conversely, seasoned teachers can also become difficult. They can become rooted in the “good old days” and refuse to modify, change, or investigate different pedagogies. They may become rigid, less pliable, and compassion and empathy reservoirs might be drained. These circumstances potentially make them burden to the system rather than an asset. Even if they do change to keep up with the times, old habits are difficult to break, and their compassion and empathy are impacted (Gonzales, 2019). But these negative sides can be turned into positive ones. The only way is openness to break the unnecessary rules that they walk on.

For these challenges, teachers have learned over time how to do things in a way that they perceive as effective and efficient. However, the reality is that with Generation Z, are the tech-savvy generation who have grown up with answers at their fingertips and video games they never could have conceived thirty years ago. They have to embrace technology and find ways to use it to meet the personality of the generation currently in our classrooms.

One way to strengthen the 21st century learning is to share with one another the pedagogical practices of seasoned and millennial teachers through LAC (Learning Action Cell) sessions. As stated in DepEd Order No. 35, s. 2016, Learning Action Cell (LAC) is a session conducted by a group of teachers who engage in collaborative learning sessions to solve shared challenges encountered in school. Such challenges may include learner diversity and student inclusion, content and pedagogy, assessment, and reporting, and 21st century skills and ICT integration. DepEd envisions that these LAC Sessions will serve as a school-based continuing professional development strategy for the improvement of teaching and learning (Cabral, 2019). Seasoned teachers can share their expertise on the content area, can also share their wisdom and ethics, how to be a good communicator and on how to be effective on classroom management. While the millennial teachers can share about the 21st Century Skills and ICT Integration, to be adaptive for change and how to be confidently enough to adopt on today's changes.

In the light of the preceding situations, this study which was gauged to determine the impact of shared pedagogical practices of seasoned and millennial teachers to strengthening 21st century learning through LAC sessions was conducted.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

This study determined the effectiveness of LAC sessions on shared pedagogical practices of seasoned and millennial teachers in strengthening 21st century learning of the teachers and the school head in Malinao Elementary School and Pulong Duhat Primary School in San Miguel North District from the EDDIS III in the Division of Bulacan during the school year 2019-2020.

Specifically, this sought answers to the following questions:

- What are the pedagogical practices that need to be developed by the seasoned and millennial teacher?
- What are the outcomes after the implementation of shared pedagogical practices of seasoned and millennial teachers through LAC sessions?
- Describe the experiences of seasoned and millennial teachers after the LAC sessions.

2. Material and Methods

This chapter presents the methods and techniques that the researcher utilized in her study. It likewise describes the subject of the study, the instruments used in gathering the pertinent data and the data processing technique applied in the analysis and interpretation.

2.1. Research Design

This study utilized the Qualitative Method specifically Participatory Action Research. Participatory Action Research (PAR) is a qualitative research methodology option that requires further understanding and consideration. PAR is considered democratic, equitable, liberating, and life-enhancing qualitative inquiry that remains distinct from other qualitative methodologies (Koch & Kralik, 2006). Sutter (2012) referenced Patton asserting, "The goal of qualitative data analysis is to uncover emerging themes, patterns, concepts, insights, and understanding".

Using PAR, qualitative features of an individual's feelings, views, and patterns are revealed without control or manipulation from the researcher. The participant is active in making informed decisions throughout all aspects of the research process for the primary purpose of imparting social change; a specific action (or actions) is the ultimate goal. The paper contextualized PAR in terms of its history, principles, definitions, and strengths, as well as the challenges and practical suggestions for using PAR. In addition, it examined focus groups, participants' observations and interviews as methods for data collection, the role of PAR in education, and the types of research for which PAR is best suited.

2.2. Data Gathering Techniques

Table 1 Timeline of the Study

PRO-CESS	ACTIVITY	PARTICI-PANTS	TAR-GET DATE	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Observe	Third Quarter Classroom Observation	Seasoned and Millennial Teacher	No-vember 18-22, 2019												
Act	LAC sessions on subject integration	Millennial Teacher	Janua-ry 24, 2020												
	LAC sessions on teaching strategies in literacy and numeracy skills	Millennial Teacher	Janua-ry 27, 2020												
	LAC sessions on teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as HOTs	Millennial Teacher	Janua-ry 31, 2020												

	LAC sessions on manages learner behavior	Millennial Teacher	Februa-ry 4, 2020															
	LAC sessions on plans, manages and implements developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes	Millennial Teacher	Februa-ry 11, 2020															
	LAC sessions on designs, selects, organize, and use diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies	Millennial Teacher	Februa-ry 17, 2020															
	LAC sessions on manages classroom structure	Seasoned Teacher	Februa-ry 21, 2020															
	LAC sessions on uses differentiated, developmentally appropriate instruction	Seasoned Teacher	Februa-ry 26, 2020															
	LAC sessions on ICT integration	Seasoned Teacher	Februa-ry 28, 2020															
Result	Fourth Quarter Classroom Observation	Seasoned and Millennial Teacher	March 4-6, 2020															

The main research instruments utilized in gathering the necessary data for this study were observation tools and researcher - made questions. The observation tools or COT – RPMS rating sheet and Observation Notes; interview guide questions and self-reflection were adapted from the PPST Manual. The COT – RPMS rating sheet consisted of indicators checklist according to how well the teacher performed during the classroom observations; and the COT-RPMS observation notes to indicate other concerns. It served as the Observation phase which was conducted by the school head. The Result of the observations became the basis of the formulation of the action plan by means of LAC session. Finally, the researcher - made questions about the teachers’ own experiences during the LAC sessions.

2.3. Sampling Procedure

The participants of the study were eight teachers and one school head from Malinao Elementary School and one teacher from Pulong Duhat Primary School, District of San Miguel North, Division of Bulacan. Total population sampling is a type of purposive sampling technique where you choose to examine entire population with characteristics.

Table 2 Participants of the Study

Participants	
School Head	1
Teachers of Malinao Elementary School	8
Teacher of Pulong Duhat Primary School	1
Total	10

2.4. Data Analysis Scheme

Once all the necessary data was completed, these were subjected to qualitative analysis. The emphasis in qualitative analysis was “sense making” or understanding a phenomenon, rather than predicting or explaining. Strauss and Corbin (2008) stressed that to further illustrate specific coding techniques – a process of classifying and categorizing text data segments into a set of codes (concepts), categories (constructs), and relationships. The interpretations were “grounded in” (or based on) observed empirical data, hence the name. To ensure that the theory was based solely on observed evidence, the grounded theory approach required that researchers suspend any preexisting theoretical expectations or biases before data analysis, and let the data dictate the formulation of the theory.

Strauss and Corbin (2008) describe three coding techniques for analyzing text data: open, axial, and selective.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the analyses and interpretations of all the data gathered in this study. It determined the effectiveness of LAC sessions on shared pedagogical practices of seasoned and millennial teachers to strengthen 21st century learning.

3.1. The Result of Third Quarter COT-RMPS Rating Scale

The strengths and improvement needs of seasoned and millennial teachers vary depending on the COT-RPMS rating scale. Through these data, the researcher described the pedagogical practice of seasoned and millennial teachers.

Table 3 Consolidated Average Rating of Pedagogical Practices of the Seasoned Teacher in COT-RMPS Rating Scale

Indicators of Pedagogical Practices	Average Rating Verbal Description
1. Applies knowledge	Very Satisfactory
2. Uses a range of teaching strategies	Outstanding
3. Applies a range of teaching strategies	Outstanding
4. Manages classroom structure	Unsatisfactory
5. Manages learner behavior	Outstanding
6. Uses differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences	Unsatisfactory
7. Plans, manages and implements developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes	Outstanding
8. Selects and uses appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT	Poor
9. Designs, selects, organizes, and uses assessment	Very Satisfactory

Table 3 shows the strengths and priority needs of seasoned teachers, ages ranging from 40-60 years old.. The table shows the strengths with outstanding ratings are in the teaching integration across curriculum; teaching strategies in developing literacy and numeracy and the critical and creative thinking, and the HOTS; management of learners’ behaviors; planning of developmentally sequenced teaching and learning; in the designing of formative and summative assessment. While ICT integration with poor ratings as well as management of classroom structure and differentiated instructions are the major needs of the seasoned teachers because they got unsatisfactory ratings to those areas. These areas for improvement of the seasoned teachers show that these are also the 21st century skills that the new students need to improve for they belong to today’s generation.

Table 4 shows the strengths and varied priority needs of millennial teachers, with ages ranged from 25-39 years old. Their strengths are in the ICT integration; management of classroom structure; and use of differentiated instructions because they got outstanding and very satisfactory ratings to those indicators. While the indicators that need improvement of unsatisfactory ratings are as follows: management of learners’ behavior; and the designing of formative and summative assessment. Other areas such as teaching integration; teaching strategies to develop HOTS; and planning a developmentally sequenced teaching and learning are the pedagogical practices that need little improvement with satisfactory ratings. This may be because these teachers are new in the educational system of the institution. Millennials

are reshaping the workplace from one where leaders use command and control to oversee their employees to a more collaborative, team-based space led by coaches “who guide and partner with employees to achieve goals” (Hodges, 2016). This new generation wants to be seen as valued partners and have mentors to bounce ideas off of to create change.

Table 4 Consolidated Average Rating of Pedagogical Practices of the Millennial Teachers in COT-RMPS Rating Scale

Indicators of Pedagogical Practices	Average Rating Verbal Description
1. Applies knowledge	Satisfactory
2. Uses a range of teaching strategies	Satisfactory
3. Applies a range of teaching strategies	Satisfactory
4. Manages classroom structure	Very Satisfactory
5. Manages learner behavior	Unsatisfactory
6. Uses differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences	Very Satisfactory
7. Plans, manages and implements developmentally sequenced teaching and learning	Satisfactory
8. Selects, develops, organizes, and uses appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT	Outstanding
9. Designs and select assessment strategies	Unsatisfactory

It is also shown to the study of Pillen, Beijaard, and Den Brok (2013) found that in their first year of teaching, beginning teachers succeeded in coping with many identity issues. Following on from Admiraal, Korthagen, and Wubbels (2000), coping was defined as trying to manage a troubled personal–environmental relationship.

Table 5 Consolidated Needs of Pedagogical Practices of the Seasoned and Millennial Teachers based on COT-RMPS Rating Scale

Pedagogical Needs of Seasoned Teachers	Pedagogical Needs of Millennial Teachers
Managing classroom structure individually or in groups	Teaching integration
Differentiated classroom instruction	Teaching strategies in literacy and numeracy skills
ICT integration in teaching	Teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills
	Manages learner behavior
	Sequence in teaching and learning process
	Formative and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements

The table 5 shows the pedagogical needs of the seasoned and millennial teachers. It shows that all indicators are visible on both generations, they already have it. All they need to do is to support one another. And it is supported by Walker (2009) when he stated that they (teachers) are extremely eager to be successful. If strong supportive programs of mentoring, induction, career ladders, and ongoing staff development are provided, they can develop into outstanding educators.

3.2. The Implementation of the LAC Sessions

LAC sessions were implemented due to the needs that arose during the third quarter classroom observations. The seasoned and the millennial teachers were found to have a lot of areas for improvement in their practices. Therefore, the school head, together with the researcher, decided to have a regular LAC session every after-class hour on shared pedagogical practices of seasoned and millennial teachers. The head teacher assigned all of the teachers in the different areas of their expertise and he himself also willingly shared things to help the teachers.

Table 6 Consolidated Improvement of Pedagogical Practices of the Seasoned Teacher.

Indicators	Average Rating Verbal Description
1. Applies knowledge	Very Satisfactory
2. Uses a range of teaching strategies	Very Satisfactory
3. Applies a range of teaching strategies	Very Satisfactory
4. Manages classroom structure to engage learners	Outstanding
5. Manages learner behavior	Very Satisfactory
6. Uses differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences	Outstanding
7. Plans, manages and implements developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes	Very Satisfactory
8. Selects, develops, organizes, and uses appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals.	Outstanding
9. Designs summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements.	Very Satisfactory

Table 6 shows that the pedagogical practices of seasoned teachers all improved based on the COT-RPMS ratings since almost all the indicators have high ratings. It implies that LAC sessions on shared pedagogical practices are essential for all teachers. It also shows that seasoned teachers can cope up with the new generation's teaching styles.

Table 7 Consolidated Improvement of Average Ratings of Pedagogical Practices of the Millennial Teacher

Indicators	Average Rating Verbal Description
1. Applies knowledge	Very Satisfactory
2. Uses a range of teaching strategies	Outstanding
3. Applies a range of teaching strategies	Outstanding
4. Manages classroom structure	Very Satisfactory
5. Manages learner behavior	Outstanding
6. Uses differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences	Very Satisfactory
7. Plans, manages and implements developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes	Outstanding
8. Selects, develops, organizes, and uses appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT	Very Satisfactory
9. Designs formative and summative assessment strategies	Outstanding

Table 7 shows that the pedagogical practices of millennial teachers all improved. It almost meets the highest expectation of outstanding rating. It also connotes that millennial teachers only needed guidance and help from the experienced ones to improve their teaching practices.

The result of the study corroborated the words of Abrams, Von Frank & Corwin, (2013), that the best ways for professionals of all generations is to work together to create a harmonious workplace. Part of the path to success is knowing exactly what needs to be done and who is responsible for each task—small or big.

3.3. New Adopted Pedagogical Practices

The new adopted pedagogical practices of seasoned and millennial teachers based on the indicators of the COT- RPMS tools are the following.

3.4. Seasoned Teacher

- Manages classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments.
- Uses differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences.
- Selects, develops, organizes, and uses appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals.

3.5. Millennial Teacher

- Applies knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas.
- Uses a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills.
- Uses a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills.
- Manages learner behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments.
- Plans, manages and implements developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts.
- Designs, selects, organize, and use diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements.

4. Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

- LAC sessions on shared pedagogical practices of seasoned and millennial teachers were found very successful because both generations improved their practices based on the results of their ratings in the conducted classroom observations.
- LAC sessions on shared pedagogical practices of seasoned and millennial teachers had very good result in COT-RPMS.
- LAC sessions on shared pedagogical practices of seasoned and millennial teachers helped to improve all teachers' pedagogical practices.
- LAC sessions on shared pedagogical practices of seasoned and millennial teachers helped to improve their teamwork.
- LAC sessions on shared pedagogical practices of seasoned and millennial teachers helped promote better perception with one another.
- It is therefore concluded that the use of LAC sessions on shared pedagogical practices of all the teachers was very effective in addressing generation gaps.

Compliance with ethical standards

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